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SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POTENTIAL IMPURITIES IN CHLOROQUINE PHOSPHATE

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ABSTRACT

The identification, characterization and control of both the processes and degradation related impurities in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs) or drug substances are the essential aspects of drug development^{2,3,4}. Complete elimination of impurities for safe human consumption has been the goal of both pharmaceutical companies and various regulatory agencies¹. Consequently, for any drug registration, one of the principal requirements is to specify both identified and unidentified impurities in drug substance/drug product as per ICH guidelines Q3A(R), Q3B(R) and Q3C [1]⁶. Characterization of impurities is required, particularly when they are present at a level higher than the identification threshold to control their levels in the final API or drug product^{1,6}.

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INTRODUCTION

The synthesis, structural elucidation and LC(liquid chromatography) method for few potential impurities of chloroquine phosphate have been documented before now in the literature but nowhere the synthesis and characterization of impurities of chloroquine intermediate has been described in writings till now⁵. In this paper, we present synthesis and characterization of three impurities identified in the lab development batches of intermediate synthesis. They include

Scheme1. Chemical structures of the impurities characterized in this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS-

IR spectra were recorded on Perkin- Elmer Spectrum One FT-IRspectrometer. 1H NMR spectra were recorded at 400 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Signals from OH groups in 1H NMR spectra recorded in CDCl₃ and DMSO were verified by the D₂O exchange^{7,8,9}. LCMS data was generated LC/MS/MS(Applied Biosystems). The mass spectral analysis was done by way of Ion Spray in positive ion mode using API 2000 LC/MS/MS system (Applied Biosystems). Perkin Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400 was used for CHN analysis. Analytical TLCs were performed on precoated mark silica gel 60 F275 plates and the spots were detected under UV light. Silica Gel (300-400 mesh) was used for column chromatography. All the chemicals were obtained from commercial suppliers and were used.

EXPERIMENTAL

Scheme2. a) Scheme for the synthesis of the 6-Chloroquinoline (Impurity 1).

b) Scheme for the synthesis of the 8-Chloroquinoline (Impurity 2).

c) Scheme for the synthesis of the 5-Chloroquinoline (Impurity 3).

Impurity1-

0.01 mole of m-chloro aniline and 0.01 mole of glycerine mixed with conc.H₂ SO₄ .Collect product, dry. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ=7.1(d, 1H), 7.4 (m, 1H), 6.8 (d, 1H), 7.7 (s, *J*=2.40 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (d, *J*=3.40 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, *J*=3.20 Hz, 1H), . MS. *m/z* =273.95 (M⁺)

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1531 (Ar C–N); 2875 (Ar C–H); 2931 (C–H); 1531 (Ar C=C)

In ¹H-NMR spectrum doublets at δ=6.8, 7.1, 7.45 and 7.87 ppm correspond to C₄-H, C₂-H, C₇-H and C₈-H protons. In addition two singlets at δ=7.7 ppm corresponds to C₅-H proton respectively. The mass spectrum of impurity **3** was recorded as additional evidence to the proposed structure and it exhibited M+1 peak at *m/z* 363.6. From all these spectral evidences the structure of impurity **3** has been confirmed. Similarly, structures of all other derivatives were established and presented in experimental section.

Impurity2-

0.01 mole of o-chloro aniline and 0.01 mole of glycerine mixed with conc.H₂ SO₄ .Collect product, dry. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ=7.1(d, 1H), 7.4 (m, 1H), 6.8 (d, 1H), 7.8 (d, *J*=2.40 Hz, 1H), 7.9 (m, *J*=3.40 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, *J*=3.20 Hz, 1H), . MS. *m/z* =273.95 (M⁺)

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1531 (Ar C–N); 2875 (Ar C–H); 2931 (C–H); 1531 (Ar C=C)

In ¹H-NMR spectrum doublets at δ=6.8, 7.1, 7.45 and 7.8 ppm correspond to C₄-H, C₂-H, C₈-H and C₇-H protons. In addition two singlets at δ=7.4, 7.9 ppm corresponds to, C₃-H and C₅-H proton respectively. The mass spectrum of impurity **3** was recorded as additional evidence to the proposed structure and it exhibited M+1 peak at *m/z* 363.6. From all these spectral evidences the structure of impurity **3** has been confirmed. Similarly, structures of all other derivatives were established and presented in experimental section.

Impurity3-

0.01 mole of p-chloro aniline and 0.01 mole of glycerine mixed with conc.H₂ SO₄ .Collect product , dry. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ=7.1(d, 1H), 7.4 (m, 1H), 6.8 (d, 1H), 7.7 (d, *J*=2.40 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (m, *J*=3.40 Hz, 1H), 7.45 (d, *J*=3.20 Hz, 1H), . MS. *m/z* =273.95 (M⁺).

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) 1531 (Ar C–N); 2875 (Ar C–H); 2931 (C–H); 1531 (Ar C=C)

In ¹H-NMR spectrum doublets at δ=6.8, 7.1, 7.45 and 7.87 ppm correspond to C₄-H, C₂-H, C₆-H and C₈-H protons. In addition two multiplets at δ=7.4, 7.87 ppm corresponds to C₃-H, C₇-H proton respectively. The mass spectrum of impurity **3** was recorded as additional evidence to the proposed structure and it exhibited M+1 peak at *m/z* 363.6. From all these spectral evidences the structure of impurity **3** has been confirmed. Similarly, structures of all other derivatives were established and presented in experimental section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the API process development of chloroquine phosphate, various process related impurities have been identified. The known impurities were synthesized, characterized and confirmed. The structural data of the known impurities were confirmed with the literature known values. Identification of impurities conducted by LC-MS followed by confirmation through synthesis of respective unknown impurities, followed by characterization by spectroscopic techniques such as ^1H NMR, IR, Mass spectroscopy. Unknown impurities presence was detected using HPLC in synthesized Chloroquine phosphate.

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